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Review Article

A Comprehensive Review On Phytomolecules Used In Formulation Of Lipstick

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ABSTRACT

The increasing consumer preference for natural and sustainable beauty products has led to the integration of plant-derived phytomolecules in lipstick formulations. This review examines the role of various herbal ingredients that provide not only vibrant, natural color but also enhance the health and protection of the lips. Key ingredients such as Aloe Vera, Beetroot, Turmeric, and Shea Butter offer multiple benefits, including hydration, anti-inflammatory effects, antioxidant protection, and natural pigmentation. Essential oils, plant-based waxes, and butters like Castor Oil, Carnauba Wax, and Cocoa Butter contribute to the texture, gloss, and stability of the lipstick, while ensuring the lips remain moisturized and protected from environmental damage. Herbal lipsticks offer a cleaner, safer alternative to synthetic formulations, aligning with the demand for chemical-free and eco-conscious cosmetics. Although some challenges exist, such as maintaining stability and controlling costs, the use of phytomolecules in lipsticks holds great promise for developing effective, natural cosmetic solutions that promote both beauty and lip health.

INTRODUCTION

Cosmetic is defined as a product that is applied to the human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness, or altering the appearance without affecting the body structure or functions. Cosmetics include beauty preparations (perfume, skin cream, nail polish, lipsticks) and

grooming aids (soap, shampoo, shaving cream, deodorant). Cosmetics can be categorized into various types, starting with skincare products like cleansers, toners, essences, serums, eye creams, moisturizers, and sunscreens. Makeup products include primers, foundations, concealers,

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powders, blushes, bronzers, highlighters, eyeshadows, eyeliners, mascaras, eyebrow products, lip liners, lipsticks, and lip glosses. Haircare products encompass shampoos, conditioners, leave-in conditioners, hair masks, styling products, hair serums, and hair oils. Nail care products include nail polishes, nail care tools, nail strengtheners, and cuticle oils. Finally, fragrances comprise perfumes, colognes, body sprays, and deodorants. Additionally, tools and accessories like makeup brushes, sponges, tweezers, lash curlers, mirrors, and makeup bags complement these products to enhance one's beauty routine.

Figure 1-cosmetics

Lipstick is the cosmetic used to color the lips. It enhances the appearance of the lips. Lipstick is used for the purpose to improve appearance, look attractive and protection of lips for many types damaging UV rays etc. lipsticks are widely used by women, it is most widely used cosmetic added in the make up to enhance the beauty of lips. A good lipstick should have persuading characteristics and be acceptable to consumer, such as having a suitable texture and antioxidant properties. Bases, oils, emollient and colorant are among the variety of components that contribute to properties of fine lipstick.

Figure 2 shades of lipsticks

Characteristics of Herbal Lipsticks

- Should cover lips adequately
- Long last effect
- Make lips soft
- Must adhere firmly to lips without being brittle & tacky
- Good degree of quality
- Completely free from grittiness
- Non-drying
- Non-irritating to skin of lips
- Desirable degree of plasticity
- Should have high retention of colours intensity without any change in shades
- Pleasant odour & flavour
- Free from sweating
- Shiny & smooth appearance
- Easily applicable & chemically

Composition

- Wax mixture
- Oil mixture
- Bromo mixture
- Colours
- Preservatives
- Fragrance
- Antioxidants
- Surfactants & other additives

Advantages of Herbal Lipsticks

- The ingredient in the natural lipstick is all natural and is safe to use.
- They also contain natural nutrient that keep lips healthy.
- They have fewer or no aspect impacts.

- They are non-toxic, highly lipophilic, anti-oxidants, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, and are used in leuco-derma of lips.

Disadvantages of Herbal Lipsticks

- Difficulty of uniform dispersion of these dye in the lipstick mass which resulting in shade variation.
- So, Amine salts of bromo acid dyes, dissolve in admixture of waxes and oils can be more uniformly dispersed.
- By Covering the lips with a coloured layer: The colour is produced by insoluble dyes and pigments, which make the film more opaque

Anatomy of Lips

Lips are soft, movable body part at the mouth of humans and helps for the intake of food and speech. "Labium superius ores" and "Labium inferiors ores", are the upper and lower lips respectively. The meeting point where the lips joint the surrounding skin of smooth area is the vermilion border and reddish area within the border is called the vermilion zone. Cupid's bow is the vermilion border of upper lips. The fleshy protuberance located in the center of the upper lip is a tubercle known by various terms including the procheilon (also spelled prochilon), the "tuberculum labiisuperioris", and the "labial tubercle".

Figure 3: Anatomy of lips

Figure 4: difference between before and after using lipsticks

Type of Lipsticks

1. Moisturizing Lipstick

Individuals who have dry lips should use moisturizing lipsticks as it keeps lips soft and smooth. These lipsticks moisturize lips due to ingredients like vitamin E, glycerin and aloe. Other great things about using moisturizing lipsticks are wet and very shiny lips.

2. Satin and sheer lipstick

These lipsticks also moisturize and nourish lips and ensure it is shiny and glossy. Sheer and satin lipsticks have high oil Ingredients and they could appear darker in the package than they are on lips.

3. Mate and Lipstick

Mate lipsticks are perfect selection for women who are seeking colorful and nice shade. These lipsticks have affectation of flat and not shiny lips.

4. Cream Lipstick

Women who'd small lips should use cream lipsticks. Lipstick with cream formula Is not shiny, but It's smooth Influence on lips.

5. Pearl and Frosted Lipstick

Frosted lipstick makes lips sparkle e and glisten. Pearl and frosted lipstick reflects light and makes very shiny effect on your own lips.

6. Gloss Lipstick

Gloss is extremely popular lipstick for girls with thin and small lips because make lips shine and Improve Vahedi mansion of depth. Gloss may be along with traditional lipstick.

7. Long Wearing and Transfer Resistant Lipstick

Women who don't have time to utilize Lipstick frequently may use long wearing lipstick. These lipsticks have formula that keep lips look per fact from 4- 8 hrs.

METHOD OF PREPARATION

1. Infusion Method:

This method involves steeping herbs in a carrier oil, such as coconut or olive oil, to extract their active ingredients.

2. Decoction Method:

This method involves boiling herbs in water or a carrier oil to extract their active ingredients. The resulting liquid is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

3. Percolation Method:

This method involves slowly pouring a solvent, such as glycerin or ethanol, through a bed of herbs to extract their active ingredients. The resulting liquid is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

4. Expression Method:

This method involves using a mechanical press to extract the active ingredients from herbs. The resulting liquid is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

5. Effleurage Method:

This method involves using animal fat to extract the active ingredients from delicate herbs. The resulting mixture is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

6. Solvent Extraction Method:

This method involves using a solvent, such as ethanol or hexane, to extract the active ingredients from herbs. The resulting liquid is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

7. Cold Pressing Method:

This method involves using a mechanical press to extract the active ingredients from herbs without heat. The resulting liquid is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

8. Supercritical Fluid Extraction Method:

This method involves using high pressure and temperature to extract the active ingredients from herbs using a solvent, such as carbon dioxide. The resulting liquid is then mixed with other ingredients to create the lipstick.

General Ingredients used in the Preparation of Herbal Lipstick

S. No	Ingredients	Quantity	Roles
1	Bees Wax	14g	Thickening Agents
2	White soft paraffin	6g	Base
3	Olive Oil	5ml	Moisturizing Agent
4	Pigment	1g	Binder
5	Acacia	1g	Additive
6	Orange Juice	1ml	Antioxidant
7	Vitamin E	1ml	Antioxidant
8	Herbal extract	1ml	Colouring Agent
9	Perfume	Q.S	Flavouring Agent

1. Beeswax

Beeswax is a product made from the honey combo the honeybee and other honey bee and other bees. Beeswax is used for high cholesterol, pain, fungal skin infection, and other conditions It used

cosmetically to hydrates, conditions, sooths, and calms the skin. It repairs damage, promotes the skin's regeneration, diminishes the appearance of the sign of aging, soothes Itchiness and irritation,

and create a hydrating, long-lasting protective barrier against environmental pollutants [20].

Biological source:

Obtained from the honey comb of the bees *Apis mellifera* and other species of *Apis* belonging family *apidae*.

Application:

- Used in cosmetics for preparation of lipsticks, face creams, Preparation of ointments.
- It is also used in preparation of lip balms It is used as lubricant for old furniture joints.

2. White soft Paraffin:

Paraffin is a soft white solid wax made from petroleum. It is used in many fields such as foodstuff and in the manufacture of candles. It is used in cosmetic in makeup product such as mascara or lipstick but also in many body care product. Liquid paraffin is hydrating and cleansing agent. Hence, it is used as one of the ingredients of after wax wipes

Biological source:

Paraffin wax is obtained from the following: Coal Petroleum, Oil shale

Application:

- Paraffin wax is used to make candles. It is also used as an additive in food items.
- It is used as a glossing, stiffening and hardening agent in lipstick.
- It is used in crayons. It is used for beauty and personal care.

3. Castor Oil:

It is rich in the mono unsaturated fatty acid ricinoleic acid, a known humectant. Humectant helps retain skin moisture by preventing water loss through the outer layer of your skin. Because of these qualities, castor oil can be applied to lips and skin, either on its own or as an ingredient, to promote hydration.[22]

Biological source:

Castor oil also called as Ricinus oil, non-volatile fatty oil obtained from the seeds of castor bean, *Ricinus communis*.

Application:

Castor oil has a various type of uses such as medicinal, pharmaceutical and industrial uses. as an additive in foods, medications, and skin care products, as well as an industrial lubricant and biodiesel fuel component

4. Orange Essence:

It keeps your lips from getting cracked and also helps in skin lightening. Orange essential oil contains limonene, which is natural and anti-inflammatory that helps heal dry, cracked lips. The orange is also refreshing on the lips.[23]

Application:

- It will help you in getting rid of dark patches around your mouth to quickly if used regularly.
- Best for dry lip and it's universal shade.

5. Vanilla Essence:

Vanilla flavor oil is high in vitamin E and natural oil, which acts as a protective lubricant on your lips and nourishes them by locking in moisture. You can use vanilla oil which isn't a true essential oil.[24]

Application:

- Vanilla has anti-inflammatory properties,
- Vanilla can help to soothe and calm irritated skin. Anti-bacterial.

EVALUATION OF HERBAL LIPSTICK:

It is very essential to maintain uniform standard for herbal lipstick, keeping this view in mind the herbal lipstick was evaluated on the parameter such as melting point, breaking point force of application surface anomalies etc.

MELTING POINT:

Determination of melting point is important as it is indication of the limit of safe storage. The melting point formulated lipstick was determined by capillary tube method, the capillary was filled and kept in the capillary apparatus and firstly observed the product was slowly melted. After some time, observed product was completely melted. The

above procedure was done in 3 times and melting point ratio was observed in all formulation

BREAKING POINT:

Breaking point was done to determine the strength of lipstick. The lipstick was held horizontally in a socket inch away from the edge of support. The weight was gradually increased by a specific value (10gm) at specific interval of 30 second and weight at which breaks was considered as the breaking point.

FORCE OF APPLICATION:

It is for comparative measurement of the force to be applied for application. A piece of coarse brown paper kept on shadow graph balance and lipstick was applied at 45°C angle to cover a 1 sq. Inch area until fully covered. The pressure reading is an indication of force of application.

SURFACE ANOMALIES:

This was studied for the surface defects, such as no formation crystals on surface, no contamination by molds, fungi etc.

AGING STABILITY:

The product was stored in 40°C for 1 hr. Various parameters such as bleeding, crystallization of on surface and ease of application were observed.

SKIN IRRITATION TEST:

It is carried out by applying product on the skin for 10 mi.

PERFUME STABILITY:

The formulation herbal lipstick was tested after 30 days, to record fragrance

PENETROMETER TEST:

Penetration on several points on the surface of the lipstick was determined and the average of all such determinations reported in micrometer. The penetrometer needle was adjusted so that it just sits on the surface of the molded lipstick rod. The needle attachment was released and the penetrating reading was recorded.

MICROBIAL TESTING:

Contamination from raw materials, moulds, storage kettles or lipstick container can lead to

microbial growth. The test consists of plating a known mass of the sample on two selected culture media specifically suitable for the growth of bacteria fungi incubating them for a specified period to permit the development of visual colonies for counting. The limit is, not more than 100 µ/gm.

RANCIDITY:

Rancidification is the decomposition of fats, oils and other lipids by hydrolysis or oxidation. It leads to obnoxious odor, bad taste & sticky product & sometimes change of color of the product. Testing of rancidity can be done by determining its peroxide number

SOLUBILITY TEST:

Dissolve the lipstick in different solvents and observe the solubility in each solvent.

pH PARAMETERS:

Determine the pH of the lipstick by using pH meter. The normal pH level for cosmetics, including herbal lipsticks, typically ranges from 4.5 to 7. Herbal phytomolecules are plant-derived compounds that offer a range of beneficial properties, making them valuable ingredients in the formulation of herbal lipsticks. Some of the commonly used herbal phytomolecules in lipstick formulations include:

1. Flavonoids

Source:

Found in fruits, vegetables, and flowers.

Function:

Flavonoids act as antioxidants, protecting the lips from environmental damage like UV radiation and pollution. They also have anti-inflammatory properties, which can soothe and calm the skin.

2. Carotenoids

Source:

Found in carrots, tomatoes, and other colorful fruits and vegetables.

Function:

Carotenoids, like beta-carotene, give natural color to lipsticks and provide antioxidant benefits. They

help to protect the skin from free radical damage and improve the appearance of the lips.

3. Tannins

Source:

Found in tea, grapes, and certain trees.

Function:

Tannins have astringent properties, which can tighten and tone the skin on the lips. They also offer mild antimicrobial benefits, keeping the lipstick formulation stable.

4. Saponins

Source:

Derived from plants like soapwort, yucca, and certain legumes.

Function:

Saponins are used as natural emulsifiers in lipsticks, helping to blend oils and water-based components. They also provide mild cleansing properties.

5. Terpenoids

Source:

Found in essential oils from plants like lavender, rosemary, and eucalyptus.

Function:

Terpenoids contribute fragrance and flavor to the lipstick, along with antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties that can help soothe and protect the lips.

6. Alkaloids

Source:

Found in plants like cocoa, tea, and certain herbs.

Function:

Alkaloids can provide soothing and healing effects, which can help repair chapped or irritated lips.

7. Polyphenols

Source:

Green tea, berries, and grapes.

Function:

Polyphenols are potent antioxidants that protect the lips from oxidative stress and help maintain their moisture and smoothness. These

phytomolecules not only enhance the therapeutic benefits of herbal lipsticks but also contribute to the natural color, texture, and overall appeal of the product. Several herbal ingredients are commonly used in the formulation of lipsticks due to their natural properties that enhance the product's color, texture, and benefits for the lips. Below are some popular herbs and natural plant-based ingredients that are used:

1. Aloe Vera

Aloe barbadensis miller (Asphodelaceae) Acts as a natural moisturizer and soothes dry or irritated lips due to its hydrating and anti-inflammatory properties. It helps in healing chapped lips.

2. Beetroot

Beta vulgaris (Amaranthaceae) is Provides a natural red pigment to lipsticks, rich in antioxidants, it also helps in enhancing the natural color of lips and offers protection against oxidative stress.

3. Turmeric

Curcuma longa (Zingiberaceae) is Known for its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, turmeric helps to protect lips from environmental damage and can add a warm, golden tint to lipsticks.

4. Cocoa Butter

Theobroma cacao (Malvaceae) is a rich natural moisturizer that helps in preventing dry and cracked lips. It improves the texture of lipsticks, making them smooth and creamy.

5. Shea Butter

Vitellaria paradoxa (Sapotaceae) is Provides intense moisturization and helps in healing chapped or dry lips. It is also rich in vitamins A and E, making it beneficial for nourishing lips.

6. Castor Oil

Ricinus communis (Euphorbiaceae) is a natural emollient that gives lipsticks their glossy finish and helps in softening lips. It also acts as a thickening agent and provides a smooth texture.

7. Carnauba Wax

Copernicia prunifera (Arecaceae) is used as a hardening agent in lipsticks, providing structure and stability. It helps to create a smooth, glossy finish and enhances the product's resistance to melting.

8. Rose Petals

Rosa damascene (Rosaceae) is used for its natural pink tint and fragrance. It also has moisturizing properties that keep the lips hydrated and adds a luxurious touch to the lipstick formulation.

9. Calendula (Marigold)

Calendula officinalis (Asteraceae) is Known for its anti-inflammatory and healing properties, calendula helps soothe and protect the lips from irritation. It is often used in formulations for sensitive skin.

10. Chamomile

Matricaria chamomilla (Asteraceae) has calming and anti-inflammatory properties, making it useful for soothing irritated or sensitive lips. It is also a natural moisturizer.

11. Beeswax

Apis mellifera (produced by honeybees) family: Apidae, Beeswax provides structure to lipsticks and creates a protective barrier on the lips, locking in moisture and preventing dryness.

12. Coconut Oil

Cocos nucifera (Arecaceae) is a highly moisturizing oil that helps soften the lips and prevent dryness. Coconut oil also has antimicrobial properties, protecting the lips from infections.

13. Jojoba Oil

Simmondsia chinensis (Simmondsiaceae) is Jojoba oil closely resembles the skin's natural sebum, making it an excellent moisturizer for lips. It is also effective in healing and repairing dry or damaged lips.

14. Saffron

Crocus sativus (Iridaceae) is used for its luxurious golden hue and antioxidant properties, saffron can

improve the appearance of lips and add a natural, healthy glow.

15. Henna

Lawsonia inermis (Lythraceae) is Provides natural reddish-brown color to lipsticks and is known for its cooling and healing properties. It can also protect lips from environmental damage.

16. Peppermint

Mentha piperita (Lamiaceae), Peppermint oil is often used for its refreshing, cooling sensation. It can help to plump lips by increasing blood circulation and adds a pleasant aroma.¹⁶

17. Lavender

Lavandula angustifolia (Lamiaceae), Lavender oil is known for its calming properties and is often used to soothe irritated skin. It also has a pleasant fragrance, making it a popular addition in lip balms and lipsticks.¹⁷

18. Green Tea

Camellia sinensis (Theaceae) is Rich in antioxidants, green tea extract helps protect lips from environmental damage and premature aging. It also has anti-inflammatory properties to soothe irritated skin.¹⁸

19. Pomegranate

Punica granatum (Lythraceae), Pomegranate extract is rich in antioxidants and natural pigments. It helps to hydrate and protect lips from free radical damage while adding a subtle color.¹⁹

20. Carrot Seed Oil

Daucus carota (Apiaceae), Carrot seed oil is rich in beta-carotene and vitamin A, which helps to maintain healthy lips and provides a slight natural tint to lipsticks. It also has anti-aging properties.²⁰

21. Grapeseed Oil

Vitis vinifera (Vitaceae). Grapeseed oil is a light moisturizer rich in antioxidants and vitamin E. It helps to protect the lips from environmental damage and prevents moisture loss.²¹

22. Avocado Oil

Persea Americana (Lauraceae), Avocado oil is deeply nourishing and hydrating. It contains essential fatty acids, vitamins A, D, and E, making it beneficial for maintaining soft and healthy lips.²²

23. Cranberry

Vaccinium macrocarpon (Ericaceae), Cranberry extract is a rich source of antioxidants and natural pigments. It adds a reddish hue to lipsticks while protecting lips from environmental stress.²³

24. Licorice

Glycyrrhiza glabra (Fabaceae), Licorice extract is used for its soothing and anti-inflammatory properties. It helps to reduce irritation and is often included in lip formulations for its skin-lightening properties.²⁴

25. Calendula Oil

Calendula officinalis (Asteraceae), Calendula oil is frequently used to soothe dry, cracked lips due to its healing properties. It is effective for sensitive or inflamed skin.²⁵

26. Cucumber

Cucumis sativus (Cucurbitaceae), Cucumber extract is used for its soothing and hydrating properties. It helps to refresh and moisturize the lips, making it ideal for lip balms and lipsticks designed for dry skin.²⁶

27. Almond Oil

Prunus dulcis (Rosaceae), Almond oil is rich in fatty acids and vitamins A and E. It helps to nourish and soften the lips, preventing chapping and dryness.²⁷

28. Cucumber Seed Oil

Cucumis sativus (Cucurbitaceae), This oil is rich in omega-6 fatty acids and vitamin E, making it ideal for moisturizing and soothing dry lips. It also helps in skin regeneration and adds a soft texture to lipsticks.²⁸ These herbal ingredients not only contribute to the color and consistency of the lipstick but also offer a range of therapeutic benefits, such as hydration, healing, and protection for the lips.

CONCLUSION

The formulation of herbal lipsticks using plant-derived phytomolecules has redefined the landscape of cosmetic products by combining natural beauty with health benefits. Ingredients like Aloe Vera for hydration and healing, Beetroot for natural pigmentation, and Shea Butter for nourishment and softness exemplify how nature's resources can enhance both the functionality and aesthetic appeal of lipsticks. These herbal components not only provide vibrant, long-lasting color but also offer therapeutic properties such as moisturizing, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant protection. Plant-based oils like Jojoba and Castor Oil improve the smoothness and gloss of the lipstick, while waxes like Carnuba contribute to the product's stability and texture. Natural colorants from Henna, Saffron, and Pomegranate offer a wide palette of shades, coupled with the added benefit of protecting the lips from oxidative stress. Herbal lipsticks cater to the growing demand for natural, sustainable, and skin-friendly cosmetics. They offer a cleaner alternative to synthetic products, reducing exposure to harmful chemicals and promoting eco-conscious beauty choices. Despite challenges such as formulation consistency and cost, the integration of herbal ingredients ensures that lipsticks provide not only cosmetic enhancement but also lip health and protection. In conclusion, the formulation of herbal lipsticks reflects a harmonious blend of nature and innovation, offering safer, more effective, and environmentally responsible beauty products. As the demand for natural cosmetics continues to rise, herbal lipsticks will undoubtedly remain at the forefront of this trend, delivering both beauty and care in a single product.

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